

Vitiligo

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Vitiligo is an acquired disorder characterised by patchy progressive depigmentation of the skin. It affects about 1% of world population and about 3% of Indian population¹. It was mentioned in *Atherva Veda* as 'Sweta kistha'². Vitiligo occurs equally in both sexes and has no age limits. It may be present as a single patch which may be progressing or static for a long time and suddenly starts progressing or multiple patches which are slowly progressing or stationary indefinitely. These depigmented macules sometimes spontaneously pigment and depigment again. The depigmented macules are often symmetrical. The etiology of non-symmetrical vitiligo, namely, segmental vitiligo is entirely different from symmetrical vitiligo vulgaris. Often the exposed areas of skin and areas around orifices of the body are depigmented rather than other areas. The etiology of above pigmentary disorder is far from clear. Many theories were however put forward. The older literature was excellently reviewed^{3,4}.

It is generally agreed that there are no functional melanocytes in the vitiligo macule³ and many theories postulate that melanocytes in the vitiligo macule are destroyed by different mechanisms in different theories³. However this is in contradiction to the published observations⁵⁻⁸ particularly the observations that transplantation of vitiligenous epidermis on the nude mice results into formation of melanin in transplanted skin and generation of melanocytes giving dopa positive reaction^{7a,8a}. These tend to refute the generally accepted notion that melanocytes in vitiligo macule are absent³. The fact that repigmentation in

transplanted vitiligo skin on to the nude mice was found in 4 out of 12 cases does not in any way reduce the conviction that often the melanocytes may remain in quiescent state in vitiligo macule^{8a}.

What are the recent hypotheses on etiology of vitiligo?

Vitiligo is a benign variant of symmetrical cutaneous lymphoma :

Goudie *et al.*⁹ suggested that the characteristic symmetrical distribution of vitiligo macules can be best explained as due to non-malignant cutaneous lymphoma. The neoplastic lymphocytes selectively home and/or proliferate at corresponding anatomical sites on the two sides of the body and that they are the forbidden clones of autoreactive lymphocytes reacting with melanocytes in the epidermis. The experimental evidence for it is however lacking.

Melatonin receptor hypothesis :

This theory assumes that melanocytes are self-destroyed in the vitiligo macule. According to this theory, vitiligo results from a cascade of reactions initiated by lack of regulation of melanin synthesis caused by activation of the melatonin receptor¹⁰. This assumption was based on the publication¹¹ that melatonin inhibits melanin synthesis without affecting tyrosinase activity. This was not confirmed later¹². In addition this observation was made in rodents. Whether human melanocytes express melatonin receptors is not known. Therefore this hypothesis is not likely to be true explanation for the etiology of vitiligo.

Vitiligo is a result of break down in free radical defence :

This theory is based on the observation that epidermis of patients with vitiligo have low catalase activity^{12a} and decreased thioredoxin reductase¹³ which may be involved in reducing free radicals at the surface of the skin¹⁴. The low catalase level was thought to damage melanocyte and thus destroy them. However it is important to mention that vitiliginous epidermis was shown to contain more than normal activity of glutathione peroxidase which can reduce hydrogen peroxide level thus decreasing adequately the supposed abnormal accumulation of hydrogen peroxide due to low catalase^{12a}.

Melanocyte abnormality in vitiligo is the cause of vitiligo :

(a) An intrinsic defect in the structure and function of rough endoplasmic reticulum in melanocytes from vitiligo human beings is proposed¹⁵. Ultrastructural studies on melanocytes from vitiligo patients demonstrated various abnormalities such as dilation of rough endoplasmic reticulum (RER), circular RER profile and membrane bound compartments of melanosomes¹⁵. These abnormalities are present not only in cultured melanocytes from vitiligo human beings but also from biopsied skin from vitiligo patients demonstrating that these changes may be real under in vivo conditions. Vitiligo occurs in many animal species in addition to humans. Progressive depigmentation with loss of active melanocytes were observed in Smith Line chickens, mice, cats, dogs, pigs, fowl and horses¹⁶⁻²¹. Abnormalities as observed in melanocytes from vitiligo subjects were also observed in melanocytes from a murine model of vitiligo¹⁷. In the case of Smith Line chickens which exhibit classic features of human vitiligo, like onset in young adulthood, variation in cutaneous expression, ocular involvement, alopecia areata like trait and spontaneous repigmentation. Vitiligo was shown to start with an inherent melanocytes defect. In this case the

defect is manifested by an increase in the activity of tyrosinase and modification of its intracellular distribution with large membrane bound compartment with numerous melanosomes and debris. In addition, melanocytes in regenerating feathers synthesise morphologically abnormal melanosomes containing pigmented extensions that are phagocytised by melanocytes in regenerating feather or choroid²². The melanocytes from vitiligo human beings also indicated focal areas of vacuolar degeneration in the lower layers of epidermis especially in the basal layer²³ of uninvolved epidermis as well as perilesional skin of untreated vitiligo subjects adjacent to normal looking melanocytes²⁴. These results were interpreted as due to production of toxic intermediate metabolites of melanogenesis produced by perhaps abnormal metabolites which destroy not only the pigment cells which produce them but also the adjoining keratinocytes²⁴. The fact that such abnormalities in keratinocytes were rarely noticed in the vitiligo lesion which is devoid of presence of any active melanocytes is a strong support, for the above interpretation.

Abnormalities in melanocytes from vitiligo afflicted animal species may have a genetic basis :

Familial cases of vitiligo are common³. An autosomal dominant pattern of inheritance with modulating factors affecting penetration and expression has been suggested²⁵. In a population where the incidence of vitiligo is higher than normal to start with²⁶ and later when this small population migrated and inbred for centuries led to a far higher percentage of incidence of vitiligo²⁷ suggesting a genetic basis for vitiligo. A genetic model postulating that recessive alleles at a set of 4 unlinked diallelic locations are involved in the causation of this disorder was proposed²⁸.

Are the defects in growth characteristics of melanocytes from vitiligo subjects sufficient cause for vitiligo? :

Since the successful methods for getting pure cultures of melanocytes from baby foreskin and

normal human beings were established^{29,30}. Attempts were made to grow these cells from vitiligo patients.

Melanocytes from vitiligo patients have abnormal growth characteristics under in vitro conditions :

Although it was generally accepted that vitiligo patches do not contain identifiable melanocytes, no attempt was made to study any abnormality of growth of melanocytes as responsible for their premature destruction by one mechanism or the other. We were the first to grow melanocytes from vitiligo subjects and to study their growth characteristics in culture³¹. The epidermis from three different regions of untreated vitiligo subjects were taken for the study of growth of melanocytes in culture. They are (a) uninvolved skin, (b) perilesional skin and (c) vitiligo patch itself.

Choleratoxin requirement for melanocytes to grow in vitro :

The epidermal cells were plated and grown as described earlier³¹. The conditions of growth of melanocytes from normal adults and vitiligo subjects were different from those used for the growth of melanocytes from the baby foreskin. The important difference was the concentration of cholera toxin (CT) that was used in the culture medium. The concentration of CT was 10^{-11} M instead of 10^{-8} M as used by others²⁹ for the growth of melanocytes from baby foreskin. It was observed by us that 10^{-8} M cholera toxin was toxic to melanocytes from adult human beings³¹. Some of the abnormalities of melanocytes from vitiligo subjects in terms of their growth, passage capacity and seeding capacity are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Growth characteristics of melanocytes from vitiligo human beings :

Melanocytes from vitiligo subjects have different characteristics of growth from the normal and in addition the cells from the vitiligo subjects differ among themselves depending on the area

from which they were taken. The melanocytes from the uninvolved area of vitiligo subjects grow with a lag period of 6–11 days and can not be passaged compared to melanocytes from normal adult human beings who grow without lag and could be passaged. The cells from the perilesional skin of vitiligo subjects do not grow at all and show abnormal morphological features³¹ compared to the cells from uninvolved skin. No identifiable melanocytes could be seen in the vitiligo patch itself³¹. It may be argued that these abnormalities are only a result of in vitro handling of these cells as in the case of seeding capacity where although the number of melanocytes in the uninvolved intact skin of vitiligo subjects are same as normal³² they were lower in the number of cells that survive after trypsinisation of epidermis from the vitiligo subjects³¹.

The abnormal growth characteristics of melanocytes from untreated vitiligo subjects are related to the disease :

That this argument is not true and that the growth abnormalities are real and related to the disease are indicated by the results presented in Table 3³³. The melanocytes from two different regions of skin from successfully treated vitiligo patients by PUVA therapy who are repigmenting are better than normal in their growth rate and passage capacity and devoid of the defective characteristics of melanocytes from untreated vitiligo subjects in terms of their seeding capacity (Table 4) lag in growth and in passage capacity (Table 3).

PUVA therapy increases growth factors in vivo :

It appears as though the melanocytes from the repigmenting vitiligo subjects were exposed under in vivo conditions to mitogenic factors since they cluster, similar to melanocytes in presence of fibroblast growth factor(s) in vitro³³, and in addition, fibroblast growth factor³³ in vitro increase the passage capacity of melanocytes

from normal human beings. A similar increase in passage capacity of melanocytes from repigmenting vitiligo subjects was seen without any addition of fibroblast growth factors in the medium suggesting that melanocytes from repigmenting human subjects might have been exposed under in vivo conditions to growth factors like fibroblast growth factors and their effect was continuing under in vitro culture conditions. This is further supported by the abnormal morphology of perilesional melanocytes of untreated vitiligo subjects similar to the morphology of melanocytes from both uninvolved area of untreated vitiligo subjects and from normal human beings after they were deprived of growth factors in culture medium in vitro. After successful treatment the perilesional melanocytes acquire normal morphology³³.

Non-availability of growth factors to melanocytes may result in vitiligo :

These results indicate that perhaps non-availability of growth factors in the perilesional area may be responsible for their abnormal morphology and their eventual disappearance in the untreated vitiligo patients expanding the area of the depigmented macule. In that case, PUVA therapy may somehow restore the availability of growth factors in the lesion and perilesional areas and perhaps elsewhere to proliferate melanocytes and their migration to dermo-epidermal junction. This would explain the faster rate of growth of melanocytes and restoration of normal morphology of cells obtained from successfully repigmenting vitiligo patients after PUVA therapy.

Repigmentation in vitiligo skin by PUVA treatment might have been a result of increased growth factor(s) for melanocytes in circulation as is indicated by the fact that serum from repigmenting vitiligo subjects increases the proliferation rate of melanocytes from normal human beings and that the serum from normal adults is more stimulatory to growth than serum from untreated vitiligo subjects³⁴. This suggestion is consistent with the observations that PUVA

increases not only the number of melanocytes in the exposed skin but also in the unexposed areas of skin³⁵ suggesting that some melanocyte growth factors increase in circulation as a result of exposure of humans to UVA or UVB.

bFGF is the natural growth factors for melanocytes :

Recent studies³⁶ suggest that basic fibroblast growth factor is perhaps the putative growth factor for melanocyte under in vivo conditions and that it is also produced by keratinocytes which are physically in contact with epidermal melanocytes. Furthermore, the synthesis of this growth factor in keratinocytes was enhanced by UVA³⁷.

Based on the antibodies for basic fibroblast growth factor neutralising the mitogenic effect of many cellular extracts on the melanocytes in culture³⁶ it is suggested that basic fibroblast growth factor is ubiquitous. We suggest that the level of bFGF in circulating blood and extracellular matrix may regulate dermal and epidermal melanocyte growth and function. In the case of the epidermal melanocytes their growth and function may be in addition regulated by the level of bFGF locally produced by keratinocytes and fibroblast. We postulate that the abnormal growth characteristics of melanocytes from vitiligo subjects could have been a result of their being deprived of sufficient bFGF for its maintenance, growth and function. This abnormality in course of time may lead to their premature destruction.

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